

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Soft clays are those which exist naturally at their liquid limits. They undergo large amount of settlement even at low values imposed stresses due to construction. Further, consolidation settlement or time dependent settlement is a problem in case of soft clays. As the permeability of soft clays is very low, drainage of pore water from the clay strata is difficult. Loose sand deposits are those which exist at low compacted densities or low relative densities. As a result, they also undergo detrimental settlements. Further, they pose the problem of liquefaction when saturated. To address these problems of weak soils various ground improvement techniques have been devised. They serve to improve bearing capacity and reduce settlements of these weak soils. To mention a few of ground improvement techniques, they are vibro compaction, stone columns, preloading with sand drains, chemical stabilization, lime soil piles and grouting. Choice of a particular technique depends upon various factors such as type of soil and degree of ground improvement.

Reinforced earth has also gained prominence recently as one of very effective ground improvement techniques. Geosynthetic reinforcement of ground has been a further recent development in reinforced earth. Geotextiles, geofabrics and geogrids have been the reinforcement components used for improving bearing capacity of poor soils. This thesis is an attempt to study bearing capacity improvement of loose sand beds through horizontal geogrid reinforcement. High density polyethylene geogrid was used as horizontal reinforcement in a loose sand bed to improve its bearing capacity. Different types of sand were used as sand beds such as fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand. A series of laboratory model tests was conducted to study the improvement in bearing capacity of these sands compacted to a relative density of 50%. A surface footing plate of diameter 60 mm was used as the shallow foundation. Circular geogrids of diameter 120 mm were used as horizontal reinforcement layers. The number of geogrids and the spacing between them were varied in the study. It was found that the bearing capacity of

loose sand layers improved with introduction of horizontal geogrid reinforcement layer. Bearing capacity was found to improve further with increase in number of geogrid layers and with decrease in spacing between them. The depth to the geogrid layer from the base of the foundation was also varied in the study.

Chapter 2 deals with a detailed review of literature on horizontal geogrid reinforcement of sand beds. Experimental investigation is presented in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 presents discussion of test results. Important conclusions from the experimental study are presented in Chapter 5.

Chapter-2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The safety and economy of any construction depends on the choice of a suitable foundation/substructure. Since this is related to the foundation soil in which the construction is done, the nature of the subsoil plays an important role on the choice of foundation. Soft clays exist all over the world. They are sedimentary soils formed under alluvial, marine, lacustrine or similar environment. Soft clays are highly compressible and possess low shear strength. They give rise to problems of instability and settlement when subjected to loads. Consequently, buildings, roads, bridges and underground construction in soft clays pose problems of design and construction.

2.2 ENGINEERING PROPERTIES OF SOFT CLAYS

Soft clays are fine-grained soils with moderate to high clay fraction and are highly plastic in nature. The natural moisture content of soft clays is often close to or greater than the liquid limit. The engineering properties of soft clays are characterized by physical properties like grain-size, Atterberg limits, consistency etc. and mechanical properties like shear strength, compressibility, sensitivity and permeability. Understanding of the behaviour of soft clay as an engineering material requires evaluation of all the physical and mechanical properties and their inter-relation to each other.

The grain-size distribution is the first step towards identification of a soft clay. High clay fraction gives high plasticity to the soil. The vast majority of soft clays contain clay-sized particles varying between 30% and 60%, the remaining grains being mainly silt-sized particles. Clay minerals have sufficient surface forces to attract water molecules. The interaction between clay minerals, water and various chemicals dissolved in water are primarily responsible for the consistency of these soils. The Atterberg limits along with the natural water content give useful identification of the consistency of clayey soil. Soft clays have natural water content generally close to the liquid limit. This is typical of all normally consolidated clays, irrespective of their depositional environment. By far the most important strength parameter influencing the stability of soft clays is that

corresponding to loading under undrained condition. As most soft clays exist permanently under the ground water table, they are fully saturated in nature and $\phi_u = 0$ condition remains valid during construction. Accordingly, the undrained shear strength of the clay determines the stability in all types of problems, e.g. bearing capacity, stability of slopes, earth pressure etc. Because of their high water content, soft clays have undrained shear strength, c_u , less than 25 kN/m^2 . In some cases the c_u of the order of $10\text{-}15 \text{ kN/m}^2$ was also measured. The determination of in-situ shear strength from laboratory tests is, however, difficult. Soft clays are highly compressible and they undergo large deformation even at low superimposed loads.

2.3 SOIL IMPROVEMENT WITH GEOSYNTHETICS

The technique of reinforcement is being extensively used, since the last two decades, in a variety of applications ranging from earth retaining structures to sub-grade stabilization. It is one of the most successful and reliable techniques and is fast replacing the other conventional ground improvement methods. The use of geosynthetics can significantly increase the safety factor, improve performance, and reduce costs over conventional alternative solutions. Reinforcement strengthens the soil by providing tension and/or lateral confinement. The reinforced ground in combination with reinforcement acts effectively in response to applied load. After the development of reinforced earth concept (Vidal, 1966) extensive efforts have been made to understand the soil reinforcement interaction mechanisms. Reinforced soil bed is a soil foundation system containing horizontally embedded geosynthetics, thin flat metal strips, rods, ties or grids. In case of foundation beds, it is widely accepted that inclusions when oriented in a definite pattern can improve the performance of the foundation soil. Over the last few decades, the use of geogrids for soil reinforcement has increased greatly because geogrids are dimensionally stable and having high tensile modulus. Results of several laboratory model tests and limited number of field tests related to the determination of the ultimate bearing capacity of surface foundation supported by multi-layered geogrid reinforcement have been reported in the literature. Binquet and Lee (1975) gave a theoretical analysis to find out the pressure intensity of isolated strip footings resting on reinforced earth slab for a given settlement (see Fig. 2.1). The reinforcements are assumed to undergo two right angled

bends at the failure surface (see Fig. 2.2). Comparison of analytical values with experimental results (Binqet and Lee, 1975) showed a fairly good. Singh (1989) and Murthy et al. (1993) modified the analysis proposed by Binqet and Lee (1975) by considering mobilized frictional and slip surfaces at the vertical planes passing through the edged of the footing. Kumar (1997) modified the work of Binqet and Lee (1975) logically for analyzing the strip footing resting on reinforced sand. Further the work was extended to square, rectangular and interfering footings. Al-Samadi (1998) extended this analysis to eccentric inclined loads also. Kumar (2002) extended the work of Kumar (1997) developing the theoretical analyses for strip and rectangular footings subjected to eccentric-inclined loads. Ramaswamy and Yong (1983) conducted model tests on strip footings on sand fill, with and without reinforcements. Bearing capacity improved and bearing capacity ratio was found to be in good agreement with the analytical procedures of Binqet and Lee (1976).

Fig. 2.1 Three modes of bearing capacity failure in reinforced earth
(After Binquet and Lee, 1975)

Fig. 2.2 Assumed failure mechanism
(After Binquet and Lee, 1975)

Guido et al (1985, 1986) conducted model plate load tests on uniformly graded sand, unreinforced and reinforced with layers of different type of geotextiles. The results showed that bearing capacity depended upon u/b ratio (ratio of depth below the footing of the first layer of reinforcement to the width of the footing), s/b (ratio of vertical spacing of the layers of reinforcement to the width of the footing) and number of reinforcement layers. Plate load tests on different sub-grades and fill material reinforced with non-woven needle punched geotextile indicated that reinforcing effect was much higher than that predicted by considering the equilibrium of deformed geotextile. Tests on strip footing resting on loose sand overlying weak clay with geotextile placed at sand-clay interface resulted in increasing bearing capacity with reduction in distance of footing from geotextile layer and increase in the embedment depth (Kim and Cho, 1988) as well as the settlement of footing. Based on the experimental model tests on geogrid mattresses (Yasufuku et al. 1996) bearing capacity improvement was formulated as a function of width of loading normalized by the effective width in the supporting soil layer. Based on

the laboratory experiments conducted by Michalowski et al. (2005) two modes of foundation collapse were suggested, one associated with reinforcement slip and the other associated with tensile failure of reinforcement. Limit analysis was applied to both cases, but only the second case yields the strict upper bound value.

2.4 STUDIES ON BEARING CAPACITY OF SAND UNDERLAIN BY SOFT CLAY

A semi-empirical method with punching mode of failure to estimate the bearing capacity of a footing on or within a sand layer overlying clay and compared the results with those from model tests on circular and strip footings and some field observations for two cases of a dense layer on a soft deposit and of a loose stratum on a firm bed. Shivashankar et al (1993) studied the improvement in bearing capacity of footings resting on granular bed overlying soft clay assuming a punching shear failure mechanism in the foundation soil. The improvement is attributed to three effects: a) shear layer effect, b) confinement effects due to interaction between sand and reinforcement in the sand layer and c) additional surcharge effects.

Fig. 2.3 Improvement of bearing capacity due to
 a) Shear layer effect
 b) Confinement effect
 c) Surcharge effect

Frictional forces developed between the soil and the reinforcements induces tensile strains in the reinforcement. The tensile strains developed provide the confining effect. This will induce additional shearing resistance along the vertical plane at the edge, which exponentially decreases with distance away from the edge of the footing.

The reclamation process is modeled as new moving boundary problem for the prediction of deformations during reclamation, by extending the Madhav and Poorooshasb (1988) model. The non-linear responses of soft sub grade soil and the granular fill are represented by Winkler springs and Pasternak shear layer respectively while the geosynthetic layer is modeled as a rough membrane. A parametric study is carried out for the deformations and tension in the reinforcing layer obtained as a function of weight of the fill, shear stiffness of the granular fill, un-drained shear strength of the sub-grade soil and the width of the reclaimed area.

Madhav and Ramu (1999) developed a new model to represent the granular bed over the soft clay deposit. Since the settlement expected in the soft clay deposits are large with the applied load, a finite deformation theory is adopted and the results agree with those obtained by the infinitesimal theory. Many model laboratory and field tests were carried out in the past to simulate the behaviour of reinforced soils. They provide a good understanding of reinforced soil behaviour. Literature shows that most of the works on reinforced foundation beds were either with planar geosynthetic reinforcement or with discrete fibres. In the present thesis, laboratory scale load tests were conducted to study the performance of reinforced foundation sand beds reinforced with geogrids as planar reinforcement. High tensile geogrid was used in the granular sand bed. The behaviour and performance of the sand bed reinforced with varying number of geogrid layers at various depths from the base of the footing was studied. Model studies were conducted in order to arrive at the load-settlement response of the reinforced sand bed.

The results indicate that the load carrying capacity of the reinforced system has increased significantly.

CHAPTER 3

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

3.1 Introduction

A laboratory scale testing is reported on. Plate load tests were conducted on different sand beds compacted to a constant relative density of 50%. Fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand were used for forming the sand beds. Horizontal geogrid reinforcement was provided beneath the test plate placed on the sand beds for studying the improvement in load-carrying capacity. Netlon CE 121 was the geogrid used for providing horizontal reinforcement. For the single geogrid reinforcement, the depth to geogrid from the base of the foundation (or test plate), indicated as 'u', was varied as 10 mm and 20 mm respectively. For the cases of number of geogrids (n) equal to 2 and 3, the spacing between the geogrids was kept constant at 10 mm. The load-settlement behavior of sand beds in unreinforced and reinforced conditions is compared.

3.2 Test materials

3.2.1 Test sands:

Fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand were the different types of sand used for forming the test sand beds. The particle size range of different sands was 0.075 mm to 0.425 mm for fine sand, 0.425 mm to 2.36 mm for medium sand and 2.36 mm to 4.75 mm for coarse sand. Fig 3.1 shows the particle size distribution curves for all the three sands. Table 3.1 shows the value of D_{10} , coefficient of uniformity (C_u) and coefficient of curvature (C_c) for all the types of sands. Based on C_u and C_c all the sands were classified as poorly graded, having the symbol SP.

Table 3.1 Properties of test sands

Property	Fine sand	Medium sand	Coarse sand
D ₁₀	0.25	0.59	1.3
C _u	1.4	1.995	2.07
C _c	1.17	1.12	1.25
Classification (USCS)	Poorly graded	Poorly graded	Poorly graded
Classification symbol	SP	SP	SP

Fig 3.1 Grain size distribution curves for all types of sands

3.2.2 Geogrid reinforcement:

Netlon CE 121 was used for providing horizontal geogrid reinforcement in the sand base. It is a high tensile polypropylene sheet with an aperture size of 6 mm. Table 3.2 shows the properties of geogrid as supplied by the manufacturer.

Table 3.2 Properties of geogrid

SPECIFICATION	RANGE
Mesh aperture size	6 x 6 mm
Mesh thickness	3.3 mm
Structural weight ($\pm 5\%$)	7.30 g/m²
Colour	Black
Polymer	HDPE
Tensile Strength	7.68 kN/m²
Elongation at max. load.	20.2%

3.3 Variables used

3.3.1 Test sand beds:

All the sand beds were compacted to a thickness of 200 mm in a cylindrical test tank of diameter 300 mm and a height of 250 mm. The relative density of all the sand beds was kept constant at 50%. The sand beds were compacted to a dry unit weight (γ_d) corresponding to the predetermined relative density of 50%. Dry unit weight (γ_d) corresponding to $D_r = 50\%$ was determined through pilot tests conducted on all the types of sand, by determining the void ratios in their loosest and densest states, namely, e_{max} and e_{min} . By prefixing the relative density at 50%, the void ratio corresponding to this relative density was first determined from the expression

$$D_r = (e_{max} - e_n) / (e_{max} - e_{min}) \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

Then the dry unit weight corresponding to the above void ratio was calculated from the expression

$$e_n = (G\gamma_w / \gamma_d - 1) \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Table 3.3 shows the values of dry unit weight corresponding to $D_r = 50\%$ for all the types of sand beds. A foundation plate or test plate of diameter 60 mm was used for the conduct of the plate load tests.

Table 3.3 Dry unit weight (γ_d) for different sands when $D_r=50\%$.

Type of sand	(γ_d) kN/m ³
Fine	15.2
Medium	14.9
Coarse	14.7

3.3.2 Geogrid reinforcement:

The diameter of the horizontal geogrid reinforcement was kept equal to 120 mm in all the tests. The number of geogrids was varied as $n = 1, 2, 3$. The spacing between the geogrid was kept constant as 10 mm. In the case of tests with $n = 1$ and $n = 2$, the depth to the top geogrid (u) from the base of the foundation (or test plate) was varied as 10 mm and 20 mm.

3.3.3 Compaction of sand beds:

All the test sand beds were compacted in the test tank to the predetermined relative density or dry unit weight, the sand beds were compacted in four layers, each of thickness 50 mm. The weight of dry sand corresponding to the dry unit weight was measured and divided in to four equal parts. Each part was compacted in the test tank to a thickness of 50 mm. In the case of geogrid reinforcement sand beds, the geogrid layers were placed at the required height, u and spacing, s . The thickness of all the sand layers was checked in order to ensure the prefixed dry unit weight. When the compaction was over, the test plate was kept on the sand bed at the center of the tank and subjected to loading.

3.3.4 Test procedure adopted:

Two dial gauges of 0.01 mm sensitivity were fixed to the test plate for observing the deformation under the applied loads. Initially, a seating load of 10 N was applied on the test plate. The subsequent load increments were 30 N, 30 N, 30 N, 30 N, 40 N and 40 N for unreinforced sand beds and 30 N, 30 N, 30 N, 30 N and 4 x 40 N for geogrid reinforced sand beds. It may be mentioned here that these load increments were chosen

arbitrarily. Each load increment was kept on the sand bed for 60 minutes and the deformations observed. The average of deformation readings observed from the two dial gauges was reported as the actual deformation. The same procedure was adopted for all the tests. The compressive load response of the sand beds was presented and analyzed in the form of load settlement curves.

Fig 3.2 Experimental setup

CHAPTER 4

DISCUSSION OF THE TEST RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

The test results presented in the form of load – settlement curves are discussed in the following sections.

4.2 Load - settlement behaviour - influence of geogrid reinforcement (n=1)

Fig 4.1 shows load - settlement behaviour of unreinforced fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand. The data indicate that medium sand resulted in punching failure undergoing a large amount of settlement under the applied maximum load. The load – settlement curve for the coarse sand was above that for medium sand indicating higher bearing capacity for coarse sand. The load –settlement curve for fine sand bed was the uppermost of all the three curves indicating maximum bearing capacity for fine sand. As fine sand resulted in highest dry unit weight, the compressive load response of fine sand was the best. As the particle size of fine sand medium is small, the soil particles get compacted to high dry unit weights for given relative densities, which resulted in higher resistance to the applied compressive loads. Though coarse sand yielded lowest value of dry unit weight owing to its large particle size and consequent large void space, it resulted in a better compressive load response than medium sand because of better bearing effect offered by the larger particles. The loads required to be applied on fine sand, coarse sand and medium sand for a settlement of 0.5 mm were respectively 63 N, 47 N and 38 N.

Figs 4.2 to 4.4 shows the load – settlement behaviour of unreinforced sand beds and sand beds reinforced with single geogrid (n=1) placed at $u = 10$ mm and $u = 20$ mm. The data pertain to fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand. The geogrid reinforced sand beds resulted in improved load – settlement behavior indicating higher bearing capacity due to geogrid reinforcement. This was true irrespective of the type of the sand, dry unit weight and particle size. Horizontal geogrid reinforcement placed beneath the footing intercepts the failure zones in sand beds and helps in increasing the bearing capacity of the foundation system. Further, the stress distribution area increases at a given depth in the

sand bed because of a wider dispersion of stress affected by horizontal geogrid reinforcement. Hence, the stress at a given horizontal plane in the sand bed reduces, resulting in a smaller amount of settlement. This leads to higher stiffness of the geogrid reinforced sand layer.

The vertical compressive stress transferred to the geogrid results in deformation of geogrid. Hence, the geogrid was observed in a deformed cup – like shape at the end of the test. The geogrid portion projecting beyond the footing edges was bent up and at the centre of the footing the geogrid was pushed down. This generates tensile forces in the geogrid. The high tensile geogrid can resist the tensile stresses effectively and can result in improved load-settlement behaviour of the system. Moreover, the interface friction and the interlocking also contribute to increase in load carrying capacity. Interface friction is friction between sand particles in contact with surface of the geogrid. Interlocking is the resistance to bending of geogrid offered by the sand particles filling the apertures. By these mechanisms the load carrying capacity of geogrid reinforced sand beds was improved (see Figs. 4.2 to 4.4). For example, the vertical compressive loads required to be applied for deformation of 0.5 mm for fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand were respectively 83 N, 44 N and 87 N.

When u was increased to 20 mm, the compressive loads required to be applied for the same deformation decreased, indicating that the geogrid would be more effective when placed in a closer proximity to the base of the foundation. The stiffness of the geogrid reinforced sand layer would be higher at lower values of u .

Table 4.1 Vertical compressive loads (N) for different cases ($\delta = 0.5$ mm)

Test case		Vertical Load (N)	% improvement
Unreinforced	Fine sand	63	--
Reinforced	n = 1; u = 10 mm	82	31
	n = 1; u = 20 mm	67	6
	n = 2; u = 10 mm; s = 10 mm	99	56
	n = 2; u = 10mm; s = 20 mm	90	43
	n = 3; u = 10 mm; s = 10 mm	94	48
Unreinforced	Coarse sand	47	--
Reinforced	n = 1; u = 10 mm	87	84
	n = 1; u = 20 mm	69	46
	n = 2; u = 10 mm; s = 10 mm	110	133
	n = 2; u = 10 mm; s = 20 mm	94	98
	n = 3; u = 10 mm; s = 10 mm	148	214
Unreinforced	Medium sand	38	--
Reinforced	n = 1; u = 10 mm	44	16
	n = 1; u = 20 mm	41	7
	n = 2; u = 10 mm; s = 10 mm	46	22
	n = 2; u = 10 mm; s = 20 mm	44	16
	n = 3; u = 10 mm; s = 10 mm	49	29

Fig 4.5 shows, by comparison, load-settlement behaviour of different sand beds reinforced with single geogrid (n=1) placed at u = 10 mm. Fine sand layer showed maximum improvement in bearing capacity. When reinforced with single geogrid, coarse sand and medium sand, in that order, inhibited a lesser improvement in bearing capacity. This is in accordance with the behaviour observed in unreinforced sand beds.

4.3 Load-settlement behaviour of sand beds reinforced with geogrids ($n > 1$):

In the cases of tests pertaining to $n = 2$, u was varied as 10 mm and 20 mm. However, in the case of $n = 3$, both u and s were kept constant at 10 mm. Figs 4.6 to 4.8 respectively show load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand reinforced with various configurations of geogrids ($n = 2$; $s = 10$ and $n = 2$; $s = 20$) for $u = 10$ mm. Similar load-settlement curves were obtained for $u = 20$ mm also. Hence, they are not being shown here. However, the load response was better for $u = 10$ mm than $u = 20$ mm for all types of sands. The load-settlement curves for $n = 1$ and $u = 10$ mm are also shown for comparison with those for $n = 2$. The load-settlement curves for $n = 2$ were above those for $n = 1$ for all types of the sands, indicating the improvement in load carrying capacity compared to $n = 1$. When the number of geogrids increased ($n = 2$), the confinement of sand layer increases resulting in higher stiffness compared to $n = 1$. The load-settlement curves ($n = 2$) lying close to X-axis reflect this. With increasing number of geogrids, the interlocking effect and interface friction increase significantly rendering the systems more shear resistant. This enables the geogrid-reinforced sand systems to withstand higher amount of compressive load more effectively when the number of geogrids increased. The bending of geogrid reinforcement observed in the case of $n = 1$ was found to be negligible in the case of $n = 2$. The higher confinement of sand, which was a consequence of higher number of geogrids, reduced the amount of settlement, thus preventing failure.

When the spacing between the geogrids (s) was less, the compressive load response was more improved (see Figs 4.6 to 4.8). When spacing between the geogrids decreased, the confinement effect increases resulting in a greater resistance to the applied load. This was observed in all types of sand. The load-settlement curves for $n = 1$ at $u = 10$ mm lay below those for $n = 2$ at $u = 10$ mm. Fig. 4.9 shows, by comparison, load-settlement curves for geogrid-reinforced fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand ($n = 2$ and $s = 10$ mm). For $n = 2$, the load-settlement behaviour was the best for coarse sand and the curves for fine and medium sands fall below that for coarse sand. This can be attributed to a higher interlocking effect obtained in the coarse sand at higher number of geogrids.

Fig. 4.10 shows the load-settlement curves for unreinforced coarse sand beds and coarse sand beds reinforced with $n = 1$, $n = 2$ and $n = 3$. The data pertain to $u = 10$ mm and $s = 10$ mm. The load-settlement curve for $n = 3$ was lying above all other curves indicating highest improvement in load carrying capacity. The curves for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$, in that order, lay below that for $n = 3$. As the number of geogrids increased, the confinement of sand increased leading to improved bearing capacity. Moreover, interlocking and interface friction also increased.

Fig. 4.11 shows by comparison the load-settlement behaviour of fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand for $n = 3$ at $u = 10$ mm and $s = 10$ mm. For $n = 3$ also coarse sand gave the best load-settlement response as in the case of $n = 2$. This shows that, while the case of $n = 1$ was more effective in fine sand, the cases of $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ were more effective in coarse sand.

Fig. 4.12 shows the effect of D_{10} of all the test sands on the compressive load (N) required for causing a settlement of 0.5 mm. The data pertain to various cases. All the curves showing the variation of compressive load with D_{10} are interestingly nearly parallel to one another, indicating a similar pattern. The curves indicate that compressive load increased with increasing particle size of the test sand bed. Thus the compressive load was highest for coarse sand. The next highest compressive load was observed in fine sands because fine sands resulted in the maximum dry unit weight. The compressive load corresponding to the medium sand was lowest. Of the various cases of geogrid-reinforced sand beds, $n = 3$ shows maximum compressive load in all types of sands. This is followed by $n = 2$ at $s = 10$ mm, $n = 2$ at $s = 20$ mm, $n = 1$ at $u = 10$ mm and $n = 1$ at $u = 20$ mm. The curve for the unreinforced sand indicates the least compressive load for all types of sand. Fig. 4.13 shows the effect of number of geogrids on the vertical compressive load required for a settlement of 0.5 mm in different types of sand. The load required for $\delta = 0.5$ mm increased with increasing number of geogrids. This was true for all types of sand. However, coarse sand resulted in the best load response followed by fine sand and medium sand.

Fig. 4.14 shows the effect of non-dimensional $d_{\text{aperture}}/d_{\text{max}}$ on compressive load required for a settlement of 0.5 mm. The data shown indicate the interlocking effect on the compressive load in various types of sand. The data pertain to unreinforced sand beds and sand beds reinforced with different configuration. The data indicate that coarse sand, having a low ratio $d_{\text{aperture}}/d_{\text{max}}$ resisted the compressive load most effectively. This was true for all cases of reinforcement. The case of $n = 3$ ($u = 10$ mm and $s = 10$ mm) resulted in the best load response.

Fig 4.1. Load-settlement behaviour of different sand beds (unreinforced case)

Fig 4.2. Load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced fine sand bed and fine sand reinforced with single geogrids (n=1)

Fig 4.3. Load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced medium sand bed and medium sand reinforced with single geogrid (n=1)

Fig 4.4. Load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced coarse sand bed and coarse sand reinforced with single geogrids (n=1)

Fig 4.5. Comparison of load-settlement behavior of different types of reinforced sand
(n=1; u=10mm)

Fig 4.6. Load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced fine sand bed and fine sand reinforced with varying number of geogrids (n=1; n=2)

Fig 4.7. Load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced medium sand bed and medium sand reinforced with varying number of geogrids (n=1; n=2)

Fig 4.8. Load-settlement behaviour of unreinforced coarse sand bed and coarse sand reinforced with varying number of geogrids (n=1; n=2)

Fig 4.9. Comparison of load-settlement behaviour of different types of reinforced sand
(n=2; u=10mm; s=10mm)

Fig 4.10. Load-settlement behaviour for coarse sand bed (n=0; n=1; n=2; n=3)

Fig 4.11. Comparison of Load-settlement behaviour of different types of reinforced sand
($n=3$; $u=10\text{mm}$; $s=10\text{mm}$)

Fig 4.12. Effect of D_{10} on the load required for a settlement of 0.5 mm.

Fig 4.13. Effect of geogrids on n (u=10mm, s=10mm) the load required for a settlement of 0.5 mm

Fig 4.14. Effect of aperture on the load for a settlement of 0.5 mm

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS

1. The load –settlement curve for fine sand bed was the uppermost of all the three types of sands, indicating maximum bearing capacity for fine sand. As fine sand resulted in highest dry unit weight, the compressive load response of fine sand was the best. Though coarse sand yielded lowest value of dry unit weight owing to its large particle size and consequent large void space, it resulted in a better compressive load response than medium sand because of better bearing effect offered by the larger particles. The loads required to be applied on fine sand, coarse sand and medium sand for a settlement of 0.5 mm were respectively 63 N, 47 N and 38 N.
2. The geogrid reinforced sand beds resulted in improved load – settlement behavior indicating higher bearing capacity due to geogrid reinforcement. The geogrid reinforced sand layer was found to exhibit higher stiffness. The vertical compressive loads required to be applied for deformation of 0.5 mm for fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand were respectively 83 N, 44 N and 87 N. The geogrid-reinforced sand layer was more effective when placed in a closer proximity to the base of the foundation.
3. The load response was better for $u = 10$ mm than $u = 20$ mm for all types of sands. The load-settlement curves for $n = 2$ were above those for $n = 1$ for all types of the sands, indicating the improvement in load carrying capacity compared to $n = 1$. The bending of geogrid reinforcement observed in the case of $n = 1$ was found to be negligible in the case of $n = 2$.
4. When the spacing between the geogrids (s) was less, the compressive load response was further improved. The load-settlement behavior for $n = 2$ at $u = 10$ mm was better than that for $n = 1$ at $u = 10$ mm. For $n = 2$, the load-settlement behaviour was the best for coarse sand and the curves for fine and medium sands fall below that for coarse sand.

5. The load-settlement curve for $n = 3$ was lying above all other curves indicating highest improvement in load carrying capacity. The curves for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$, in that order, lay below that for $n = 3$. For $n = 3$ coarse sand showed the best load-settlement response as in the case of $n = 2$. While the case of $n = 1$ was more effective in fine sand, the cases of $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ were more effective in coarse sand.
6. Compressive load increased with increasing particle size of the test sand bed. Hence, the compressive load was highest for coarse sand. The next highest compressive load was observed in fine sands because fine sands resulted in the maximum dry unit weight. The compressive load corresponding to the medium sand was lowest. Of the various cases of geogrid-reinforced sand beds, $n = 3$ showed maximum compressive load in all types of sands. This is followed by $n = 2$ at $s = 10$ mm, $n = 2$ at $s = 20$ mm, $n = 1$ at $u = 10$ mm and $n = 1$ at $u = 20$ mm.
7. The load required for $\delta = 0.5$ mm increased with increasing number of geogrids. This was true for all types of sand. Coarse sand resulted in the best load response followed by fine sand and medium sand.
8. The effect of non-dimensional ratio $d_{\text{aperature}}/d_{\text{max}}$ on compressive load required for a settlement of 0.5 mm indicated that the interlocking effect was highest in the case of coarse sand. As coarse sand has a low $d_{\text{aperature}}/d_{\text{max}}$ ratio, it resisted the compressive load most effectively. This was true for all cases of reinforcement.

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